

SPREAD OF INTERNAL PARASITES AMONG THE STUDENT OF AL -SHAHEED AL-NOMAN
SCHOOL, WIDI JADEED VILLAGES, TAIZ PROVINCE -REPUBLIC OF YEMEN

Majed A. Noman¹, Samer A. Alshargby² and Hussien O. Kadi³, Thayer Mansoor, Rafeeq A. Rahman, Gareer S. Abudo, Gamel A. Aon and Mohamd A. Soltan.

¹ Depart. of Pharmaceutics, Faculty of Pharmacy, Sana'a University.

² Depart. of Hematology, Faculty of Medicine, Sana'a University

³ Depart. of Pharmacology, Faculty of Medicine, Sana'a University.

ABSTRACT

The study was conducted in February 2006 in Taiz city which considered one of the endemic areas of Schistosomiasis due to high population and short governmental services that enhance the spread of infestation particularly in Wadi Jadeed area where ponds, rivers, snails, no sewage's system, no water project, absence of personal hygiene and illiteracy. The objective is to study the spread of internal parasites among the student of AL -Shaheed Al-Noman school, Widi Jadeed villages, Taiz province, Yemen. The field study was conducted on 210 student and details questionnaire information and clinical examination were connected. Millipore filtration technique and modified Kato-Katz techniques were adopted for urine and stool analysis. Results show that most common parasites and prevalence rate were arranged in descending manner as follows *Ascaris lumbricoides* (23.81%) > *Entamoeba Coli* > *entamoeba Coli* (21.91%) > *Giardia* (14,28%) > *Trichuris trichiura* (13,33%) > *Entamoeba histolytica* (10.95%) > *Hymenolepis nana* (10,96%) > *Enterobius* (2.85%) > *Taenia saginata* (1.90%). There was no effect of parent's education, sources of water availability and usage of toilets (baths) on the rate of infestation. The virulence of Schistosomiasis infestation has varied with the type of activity at site of water resources and with the frequent of going to the source of water.

KEYWORDS: Schistosomiasis, Wadi Jadeed area, Common parasites, Clinical examination, Yemen

INTRODUCTION

An increase of infestation in population of certain area due to irrigation which are a good media for intermediate host (the snails) to spread and subsequently, Thus increase the rat of investment among population particularly at the country side.

Schistosomiasis is second to malaria in the list of major public health problems in Yemen (YPHD 1995) and intestinal schistosomiasis has been reported in a number of different surveys (Schaap et al., 1992).

Various studies in Yemen have been conducted on the different parasites and show that the prevalence of *Entamoeba histolytica* ranged from 1.7%–36% (Raja'a YA et al., 2001 ; Farag 1985), *Giardia lamblia* 9.0%–20.5%, *Hymenolepis nana* 2%–8.3% (Azazy and Al-Taiar 1999 ; Azazy and Al-Dullaimi 1999) and lowest prevalence was 0%-2% for *Enterobius vermicularis* (Farag 1985; Azazy and Al-Taiar 1999).

Taiz city is considered one of the endemic area of Schistosomiasis due to presence of many factors that enhance the spread of infestation (Hazza et al.,1983) and particularly in Wadi Jadid area due to presence of ponds, rivers, snails and were no sewage's system, no water project also shortage in personal hygiene and illiteracy. Concerning other intestinal parasites such as *ascaris*, *entamoeba*, *giardia*, *taenia saginata*, *hymenolepis nana*, *trichuris*, *trichiura*, *enterobins* present in tropical and subtropical areas, due to lack of health education, personal hygiene and other factors which resulted in existence such parasites and causing deterioration to health levels. Yemen is also consider as an endemic area for such helminthes (WHO 1993).

Also these infection were reported from areas such as Sana'a (YBCP, 1993), Marib (Nagi and Molan 1992), Ibb (Raja'a et al., 2000) and Hajaja (Azazy and Al-Dullaimi 1999) cities.

Studies in different parts of Yemen have reported prevalence rates of ascariasis ranging from 16%–68% (Farag 1985 ; Azazy and Al-Taiair 1999).

Meanwhile, trichuriasis was reported, mostly from the same areas, in 1%–21% of the population (Raja'a et al., 2001 ; Azazy and Al-Dullaimi 1999).

Schistosomiasis ranks second only to malaria in terms of parasite-associated human morbidity and mortality (Wilkins 1987). It is the most prevalent of the water borne parasitic diseases and one of the greatest risks to health in rural areas of the developing world and also the most widespread of all human diseases but with low morbidity rate (WHO 1990).

The objective of this study is to measure the rate of spread of internal digestive system's parasites, spread and virulence of infestation of students with schistosomiasis under an influence of social behavior, economical and educational factors which help in spread and increase virulence of infestation within the students of Al- Shaheed Al- Noman school in Wadi Jadeed Taiz City.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This is descriptive study in sector and the samples value was 210 students aged between 7-17 years. The study was carried out in Taiz governorate which lies in the remote south of Yemen, 250 km from the capital city, Sana'a. Al-Shaheed Al-Noman's School which located in Wadi Jadeed was selected because it near running unhealthy water sources and serve the students comes from the surrounded seven villages named Wadi Jadeed, Wadi Arsh, Al-Arsoom, Al- Hawgalah, Al- Shagarah, Al- Ramda and Kalaba, with population of 5000 residence, most of them are farmers, depending on rain fall and wells waters. Health services are not available in such villages and people depending on health services available in a nearby city. The examination team visited the school and the villages and collecting detailed personal and behavioral information data which is based on geographical, social, economic, environment and clinical information obtained from students and their parents in the form of Arabic questionnaire designed for this purpose.

Clinical examination to the student for spleen and liver was done to explore any enlargement in spleen or liver, by measuring and calculation of the degree of their pendulous on the ribs edges in cm using metric measurement.

Midday urine and stool samples were collected from each individual in containers labeled with name and number and taken back to the university laboratory for examination. Urinary schistosomiasis examination was carried according to Millipore filtration technique (WHO 1993) as (n) eggs/10 ml urine. For stools examination, modified Kato–Katz techniques was applied and results were reported as (n) eggs/g of feces (Teesdale and Amin 1976). While microscopical examination was carried out for gastrointestinal parasites such as *ascaris*, *entamoeba*, *giardia*, *Taenia saginata*, *hymenolepis nana*, *trichuris*, *trichiura*, *enterobins*, *schistosomiasis mansoni* (*Biomphalaria pfeifferi*) and *schistosomiasis hacmatobium* (*Bulinus globosus*) and their relation to parent's education, water resources activity were studied.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Total number of student that participated in this study were 210 male students. Thier ages range from 6-17 years, while female did not enrolled them selves in school except in very law numbers. So the category of students enrolled in the study aged between 6- 15 years as illustrated in Table 1.

Table 1: Distributions of students according to the age.

Age (years)	No	%
0 –6	22	10.5
7 –12	149	71.0
13 –17	39	18.5

Table 2: Distributions of the students inrolled in the study according to their seven villages.

Village Name	Student No.	Percentage %
Wadi Jadeed	80	38.10
Wadi Arch	19	9.05
Al-Arsoom	34	16.19
Al – Howgalah	34	16.19
AL-Shagarah	9	4.29
AL-Ramda	12	5.71
Kalaba	22	10.48
Total	210	100

Table 3 : Parent's level of education (Father and mother).

Parents	Father and mother Education levels											
	Illiterate		Read		Primary		Int. mediate		Secondary		University	
	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%
Fathers	115	54.8	41	19.5	25	11.9	13	6.2	7	3.33	4	1.9
Mothers	178	84.8	25	11.0	5	2.3	2	0.95	0	0	0	0

As illustrated in Table 3. Parent's level of education shows that 52.8% and 84.3% of fathers & mothers respectively are illiterate. 19.5% and 11.0% of fathers and mothers respectively only can read and their level of education as follows, 11.9 % and 2.5% primary, 6.2% and 0.92% inter mediate, 3.3% and 0.0% secondary and 1.9 % and 0.0% university levels respectively.

Table 4: Fathers occupations(Farmers, employed, monthly paid, general labore. Unemployed and dead.

Parents	Fathers occupations											
	Farmers		Daily employed		Monthly Paid		General laborer		Un-employed		Dead	
	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%
Fathers	101	48.2	74	35.1	26	12.4	3	1.5	2	0.9	4	1.9

As in Table 3, fathers occupations study show that; 48.2 % are farmers, 35.1 % daily employed, 12.4 % monthly paid, 1.5 % general laborer, 0.9 % unemployed and 1.9 % dead.

Table 5: Student residence water types and their activity in water sources.

Student residence water						Student activity in water sources											
HavingWater Project		Running water		Unhealthy water		Go for Swimming		Having a bath		Bring water		Washing cloth		Urinate & deficit		More than activity	
No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	N	%	No	%	N	%	No	%
170	80.	35	16	5	2.5	53	25.4	5	2.2	1	6.4	23	10.9	6	2.7	110	52.4

Table 5 shows that, 80.7 % of students residence having water project, 16.8 % depending on running water and 2.5 % using unhealthy water sources and the activity of student at water resources show that, 25.4% go for swimming, 2.2% having a bath, 6.4% bring water, 10.9% washing clothe, 2.7% go to urinate and deficit and 52.4% practicing more than one activity .

Table 5: Defecation and role of using toilet by students.

Role of students in defecation and using toilet											
Defecate in bath		In valley		Near houses		In the street		In a pound		Any where	
No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%
47	22.4	85	40.5	33	15.7	11	5.2	8	3.8	26	12.4

As in Table 5, Defecation and role of using toilet show that, 22.4% defecate in bath, 40.5% in valley, 15.7% near houses, 5.2% in the street, 3.8% in a pound and 12.4% any where.

Table 6: Rate of spread of clinical symptoms within the students.

Rate of spread of clinical symptoms within the students											
Abdominal symptoms		Headache		Itching		Bloody stool		Blood urine		Skin symptoms	
No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%
174	82.85	145	69.05	90	42.86	72	34.28	40	19.05	36	17.14

As illustrated in Table 7. The rate of spread of clinical symptoms within the students show that, 174 (82.85%) student sever from abdominal symptoms, 145 (69.05%) headache, 90 (42.86%) itching, 72 (34.28%) bloody stool, 40 (19.05%) blood urine and 36 (17.14%) having skin symptoms.

Table 8: Spreading of hepatomegaly and splenomegaly among students.

Hepatomegaly (liver) and splenomegaly (spleen) among student.													
Type of Disease	Normal size liver&spleen		1cm enlarged		2cm Enlarged		3cm Enlarged		4cm enlarged		5cm enlarged		
	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	
Hepatomegaly	149	70.95	12	4.8	18	7.2	10	4.76	16	6.4	5	2	
Splenomegaly	199	94.76	2	0.95	1	0.05	4	1.99	1	0.05	3	1.40	

As hepatomegaly is concern 149 (70.95%) student show no liver size enlargement, while those sever from hepatomegaly, 12 (4.8%) student with 1cm enlarged liver, 18 (7.2%) enlarged 2cm, 10 (4.76%) enlarged 3cm, 16 (6.4%) enlarged 4cm and 5 (2%) enlarged 5cm. For splenomegaly, 199 (94.76%) students show no spleen size enlargement, while 2 (2%) enlarged 1cm, 1 (2%) enlarged 2cm, 4 (1.6%) enlarged 3cm, 1 (0.4%) enlarged 4cm and 3 (1.2%) enlarged 5cm. as shown in Table 8.

Table 9: Relationship between rate of infestation with *S. haematobium* and with *S.mansoni* & location of villages.

Villages	<i>S. haematobium</i>				<i>S. mansoni</i>			
	Infested		Not ifvested		Infested		Not ifvested	
	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%
Wadi jadeed	7	3.33	73	34.76	26	12.38	54	25.71
Wadi Arch	1	0.48	18	8.75	4	1.90	15	7.14
Al-Arsoom	4	1.91	30	14.29	20	9.52	14	6.67
Al – howgalah	5	2.38	29	13.81	14	6.67	20	9.52
AL-shagarah	0	0.00	9	4.29	3	1.43	6	2.83
AL-Ramda	0	0.00	12	5.71	2	0.9	10	4.76
Kalaba	2	0.95	20	9.52	9	4.29	13	6.19

The most infected villages by *S. haematobium* is Wadi jadeed which is the near vilage to the water sources followed by Al- Arsoom, Alhowgala, Kalaba, Al-ramda and Alshagrah respectively. For *S. mansoni* is Wadi jaded, Al rasoom, Alhawgala, Kalaba, Wadi alrch and Al-ramda as shown in Table 9.

Table 10: Relationship between rate of infestation with *S. haematobium* and *S. mansoni* with parent's education level

No	Type of infestation	Parents	Educations	Infested		Not Infested		Total
				No	%	No	%	
1	<i>S. haematobium</i>	Father	Educated	5	2.38	8	3.8	Chi Sq=0.30 P= 0.16
			Non	8	3.80	116	55.23	
		Mother	Educated	2	0.95	29	13.8	
			Non	14	6.66	28	13.33	
Total				29	13.80	181	86.20	
2	<i>S. mansoni</i>	Father	Educated	28	13.33	27	12.85	Chi Sq=2.86 P= 0.90
			Non	36	17.14	65	30.95	
		Mother	Educated	8	3.80	24	11.42	
			Non	7	3.33	15	7.14	
Total				79	37.6	131	62.40	

Table 10 shows relationship between rate of infestation with *S. haematobium* and parents education. Whereas (P) value > 0.05. Therefore there is no difference of statistic significance between rate of infestation with *S. haematobium* and parent's education. By review of previous studies we found that the rate of infection was high with the students their father's educational level is lower than those students whom their father's educational level are higher. This relationship requires further study and analysis. However the overall prevalence rate of *S. haematobium* in AL-Shaheed Al-Noman school, Widi Jadeed villages, Taiz province is much less than that recorded in Yemen 1982 (64.6S%) (Nagi and Molan 1992), Zimbabwe 15.2% (Taylor and Makura 1985), Saudi Arabia 1.13% (Ghandour *et al.*, 1991), Sudan 60.85% and Egypt 55,74% (Abdel-Wahab *et al.*, 1980).

Table 11: Distribution and rate of infestation with *S. haematobium* and *S. mansoni* in relation to availability and usage of toilets. where p >0.05

No	Type of infestation	Availability and usage of toilets	Infested		Not Infested		Total
			No	%	No	%	
1	<i>S. haematobium</i>	Available and used	12	5.71	153	72.86	Chi Sq= 7.19
		Available and not used	3	1.43	6	2.86	
		Not available	4	1.905	32	15.23	
Total			19	9.05	191	90.95	
2	<i>S. mansoni</i>	Available and used	55	26.19	107	50.95	Chi Sq=0.99
		Available and not used	2	0.95	8	3.81	
		Not available	14	6.66	24	11.43	
Total			71	33.81	139	66.19	

As illustrated in Table 11. The study shows the distribution and rate of infection with *S. haematobium* and *S. mansoni* in relation to availability and usage of toilets among students who have W.C (Toilets) and use it are 5.71% and 26.19%, students who have W.C. but they do not use it 1.43% and 0.95% and among those students who have not a toilets 1.91% and 6.66% respectively.

Table 12: Relationship between the infestation of *S. haematobium* and *S. mansoni* with frequent of going to water resources.

No	Type of infestation	Student going to Resources	Invested		Not Invested		Total
			No	%	No	%	
1	<i>S. haematobium</i>	Did not go	4	1.905	67	31.90	ChiSq =11.3 P = 0.022
		Some time go	5	2.38	12	5.71	
		Always go	8	3.809	114	54.28	
Total			17	8.1	193	91.9	
2	<i>S. mansoni</i>	Did not go	6	2.85	62	29.53	ChiSq=32.0 P = 0.0007
		Some time go	10	4.77	7	3.33	
		Always go	59	28.09	66	31.43	
Total			75	35.71	135	64.29	

Table 12 shows that the rate of infection with *S. haematobium* among those student who go to the water resource is greater than those who did not go to water resource. So social pattern is one of the reasons that males student

in our study showed apparent higher levels of *S. haematobium* prevalence, because males have much greater contact than females specially in swimming, farming and agricultural and other activities. This result is in agreement with other findings (Taylor and Makura 1985; Ghandour *et al.*, 1991; Mansour *et al.*, 1982 and King *et al.*, 1982) with as the value of (p) was less than 0.05. whereas P value > 0.05, therefore there is no difference of statistic significance between rate of infestation with *S. mansoni* and the frequent of going to water resources.

Table 13: Distribution of rate of infestation for each parasite

Type of Parasite	No	%
<i>Ascaris</i>	50	23.81
<i>Entamoeba Coli</i>	46	21.91
<i>Entamoeba histolytica</i>	23	10.95
<i>Giardia</i>	30	14.28
<i>Taenia saginata</i>	4	1.904
<i>Hymenolepis nana</i>	23	10.96
<i>Trichuris trichiura</i>	28	13.33
<i>Enterobius</i>	6	2.85
Total	210	100 %

The highest intestinal parasite detected among infected students was *Ascaris lumbricoides* and this agrees with that reported by (Azazy and Raja'a 2003). Followed in descending manner by *Entamoeba Coli* > *Giardia* > *Trichuris trichiura* > *Entamoeba histolytica* > *Hymenolepis nana* > *Enterobius* > *Taenia saginata*.

CONCLUSION

High rates of infection with protozoa and helminth parasites indicate high levels of pollution in the environment of the study area.

More efforts are needed to improve environmental sanitation, health education and urgent control of Schistosomiasis, protozoa and helminth parasites in the area of study in order to reduce the rate of infestation and reduce health problems.

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Corresponding author

Maged A. Noman, Yemen University. P.O. Box: 13893 Sana'a, Republic of Yemen.

E-mail: magedalwan65@gmail.com